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Research Article

**HOW EFFECTIVE IS ZIEHL-NEELSON STAINING IN
COMPARISON WITH LOWENSTEIN JENSEN CULTURE FOR
DETECTING ACID FAST BACILLI?**¹Dr. Muhammad Ali, ²Dr. Nouman Anees, ³Dr. Mariam Ilyas¹Student of MCPS (HCSM), College of Physicians and Surgeons Karachi, Pakistan.²Indus Hospital, Manawan, Lahore³DHQ Hospital Narowal**Abstract:****Objective:** To evaluate false negativity rate of Ziehl-Neelson smear microscopy.**Methodology:** This descriptive study was performed at Mycobacteriology laboratory of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi during June 2017 to March 2018. 3951 was study sample. Out of these 3951 cases, 2773 cases had pulmonary tuberculosis while 1178 were extra pulmonary tuberculosis cases. Study population was selected from suspected cases of tuberculosis referred to laboratories from the outdoor clinic of pulmonology as well as internal medicine department and neighboring referral health facilities. Follow up cases were not included in study sample. LJ media was considered the standard to test the false negativity rate of ZN smear microscopy.**Results:** Most common sample was sputum 48.5%, followed by pleural fluid 12% and pus 8.3%, respectively. 23.1% samples were false negative out of which pulmonary samples were 19.6% and extra pulmonary samples were 29.2%. P value was statistically significant <0.001. False negativity rate of following samples was most common; pericardial (40%), synovial (38%), pleural fluids (33%) and pus (32%), respectively.**Conclusion:** ZN staining technique has high false negativity rate, especially in patients with low mycobacterial load. National TB control program should adopt more efficient diagnostic methods for diagnosing tuberculosis instead of ZN staining.**Keywords:** Tuberculosis, Ziehl-Neelson Smear, False negative, Microscopy.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Muhammad Ali,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis is one of the major problems in subcontinent. During the year 2013, around 2 million deaths were estimated due to tuberculosis [1]. The causative agent *Mycobacterium tuberculi*, is an acid fast bacillus. Disease involves many organs and systems of body. The most common form of tuberculosis is pulmonary tuberculosis which spreads through droplet infection. Due to its easy transmissibility to the contacts this form of tuberculosis is the most common. Other forms of tuberculosis involve bones, lymph nodes, intestine, meninges etc.

In countries with higher tuberculosis burden, there is need for rapid and effective detection of mycobacteria from respiratory samples and other body secretions like pus, BAL, urine, CSF. A computer aided whole smear screening system has been launched in other countries which provides real time images and diagnostic grades from fluorescence microscopy as well as bright light microscopy, for detection of acid fast bacilli. This new computer based detection system has high sensitivity. In a research conducted by Law YN, et al 288 out of 488 patients were detected positive by using this technique. It also helped in reducing laboratory technicians' workload by reducing manual work [2].

A retrospective analytic cross sectional study was conducted in Tripoli- Libya by Shoukrie A, et al in 2018, in which sensitivity of ZN smear microscopy was compared with LJ media and it was concluded that ZN staining has very low sensitivity in detecting acid fast bacilli, LJ culture is the gold standard for detection of acid fast bacilli [3, 7].

Due to cost effectiveness and less time consumption, ZN smear microscopy is widely used in Pakistan for detection of acid fast bacilli. So, a need was felt to study the sensitivity of ZN smear microscopy. Pakistan has high tuberculosis burden, there is a need to launch more sensitive diagnostic techniques which can reduce the false negativity rate and help in accurate diagnosis of tuberculosis patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was conducted over the period of ten months in Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, Pakistan. The objective and study details were approved by ethical review board of hospital research department. 3951 patients, who were referred for diagnosis of tuberculosis to mycobacteriology laboratory, from pulmonology and internal medicine

departments and also from surrounding referral health centers were included in the study. Out of 3951 patients, 2773 were suspected cases of pulmonary tuberculosis while 1178 patients had extra-pulmonary tuberculosis. Pulmonary tuberculosis suspects presented with sputum, broncho-alveolar lavage samples, while extra-pulmonary tuberculosis suspects presented with pus, CSF or pleural fluid, ascetic fluid, pericardial fluid, synovial fluid and urine. Only those samples were enrolled which were referred by a registered medical practitioner, as strong tuberculosis suspect. The strong tuberculosis suspect was defined as productive cough for more than 3 weeks, with or without evening hyperthermia for more than 2 weeks, weight loss, chest x-ray findings suggestive of tuberculosis. Follow up cases, old TB cases who were under-treatment were excluded from study. Specimen collection was done under expert supervision following WHO protocols. ZN staining and LJ staining was performed on each specimen. After LJ staining, specimens were observed for 48 hours. Mycobacterial growth was observed after every week for 8 weeks.

Control slides of ZN stain were made from every batch of ZN. Each specimen was tested twice by two laboratory technicians under light microscope. Slide preparation was done according to WHO guidelines. Few random positive and negative slides and doubtful slides were counter-checked by expert microbiologist in order to reduce the error and to improve result quality. Culture media quality was tested by using ATCC (American Type Culture Collection) strains of H37rv.

Data analysis was done on SPSS version 21. False negativity rate of ZN smear was confirmed by using LJ culture media. Chi square test was applied. P-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Most common sample was sputum 48.5%, followed by pleural fluid 12% and pus 8.3%, respectively. 23.1% samples were false negative out of which pulmonary samples were 19.6% and extra pulmonary samples were 29.2% [table:1]. P value was statistically significant <0.001. False negativity rate of following samples was most common; pericardial (40%), synovial (38%), pleural fluids (33%) and pus (32%), respectively [table: 2].

The results of study are presented in the form of tables.

Table:1 False negativity rate of ZN staining.

Specimens			LJ positive	LJ negative	Total	Fp	Fn	Significance
Extra-pulmonary	ZN	Positive	118	1	119	.8%	29.2%	Chi square 289.9 P value .0001
		Negative	310	749	1059			
		Total	428	750	1178			
Pulmonary	ZN	Positive	868	8	876	.9%	19.6%	
		Negative	378	1524	1897			
		Total	1241	1532	2773			
Total	ZN	Positive	986	9	995	.9%	23.1%	
		Negative	683	2273	2956			
		Total	1669	2282	3951			

Table:2 ZN smear false negativity of each specimen.

Specimen				LJ positive	LJ negative	Total	Fp	Fn
Pulmonary	Sputum	ZN	Positive	708	5	713	.7%	23.3%
			Negative	281	921	1202		
			Total	989	926	1915		
	Broncho-alveolae lavage	ZN	Positive	160	3	163	1.8%	13.2%
			Negative	92	603	695		
			Total	252	606	858		
Extra-pulmonary	Urine	ZN	Positive	3	0	3	0%	24.4%
			Negative	12	37	49		
			Total	15	37	50		
	Synovial fluid	ZN	Positive	1	0	1	0%	38.2%
			Negative	13	21	34		
			Total	14	21	35		
	Pericardial fluid	ZN	Positive	5	0	5	0%	40%
			Negative	14	21	35		
			Total	19	21	40		
	Ascetic fluid	ZN	Positive	7	0	7	0%	15.6%
			Negative	20	108	128		
			Total	27	108	135		
	CSF	ZN	Positive	11	0	11	0%	16.6%
			Negative	17	85	102		
			Total	28	85	113		
	Pus	ZN	Positive	26	0	26	0%	32%
			Negative	97	206	303		
			Total	123	206	329		
	Pleural fluid	ZN	Positive	65	1	66	1.5%	33.4%
			Negative	137	273	410		
			Total	202	274	476		

DISCUSSION:

Per year almost 10.4 million new cases of tuberculosis appear across the globe and almost 1.4 million deaths occur due to it [4]. According to a survey conducted in 2017, 2 to 10% of population of Pakistan is suffering from tuberculosis, which means every 10 persons out of 100 has the tuberculosis and are a threat to spread the disease to contacts. The risk factors for tuberculosis are poverty, low socioeconomic status, over-crowding, smoking, immuno-compromised state, less effective use and

practice of vaccination, less effective provision of health care to patients living in far flung areas [7,10].

A comparison between sensitivity of ZN smear and fluorescence microscopy in detection of AFBs was done by Gupta S, *et al.* and the conclusion was in favor of fluorescence microscopy, in regard to sensitivity [5]. Similar comparison was studied by Laifangban S, *et al.* in which false negativity rate of ZN staining was 40.8% while AO staining had only 2.3% false negativity rate [6]. Fluorescence

microscopy reduces the mycobacterium detection time to half in comparison with ZN staining. In addition, its sensitivity is better than ZN smear microscopy [8,9].

Scientists are looking for more efficient and less time consuming diagnostic techniques for detection of AFBs. Direct microscopy results were compared with the bleach sedimentation technique in a research study at Nigeria, in which sensitivity rates were 28.8% and 30.3% for both techniques, respectively. Hence it was proved that bleach sedimentation has better results than direct microscopy [11].

CONCLUSION:

ZN staining technique has high false negativity rate, especially in patients with low mycobacterium load. National TB control program should adopt more efficient diagnostic methods for diagnosing tuberculosis instead of ZN staining.

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